

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE & ARTS

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Tomillus et guarnieri.

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Research Centre for European Philological Tradition
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Cover: graphic reworking of image number 2 of Leena Löfstedt's article, courtesy of Dr. Elizabeth Morrison, Senior Curator of Manuscripts, J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles (manuscript Ludwig XIV.2).

The marginal note states *Nota illud esse guarnerii* 'NB That belongs to Garnier'. The adjacent text Decr. C 10 q 2 c 2 § 11 reads *Si yconomus ecclesiae*

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Prof. Carla Rossi

University of Zurich

& Research Centre for European Philological Tradition

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Baal's other priest

LEENA LÖFSTEDT

Before Thomas Becket's return from his exile it had been agreed that Henry II would grant him and his men a safe return to England and restore to the archbishop and the archdiocese their rights and their possessions. As Thomas returned, he soon noticed that the situation in England did not correspond to Henry II's promise. He wrote about it to the Pope, adding:

Quod tamen non tam illi credimus imputandum quam sacerdotibus Baal... qui tocius discordie in-centores ab initio extiterunt. Sed horum omnium primicerii sunt Eboracensis ille et episcopus Lunden-sis...

("Yet we do not think that this action should be imputed to him (sc. to the English King), but to the priests of Baal... who from the beginning have been the instigators of all the dissension. The leaders of all these followers of Baal are that notorious York and the bishop of London" Duggan 2000, 2 : 1344–1345, letter 326).¹

The bishop of London, *episcopus Lunden-sis*, Gilbert Foliot, is well known to Thomas Becket's early hagiographers. Garnier (or Guernes) de Pont-Sainte-Maxence² lets his reader understand that Gilbert Foliot and Thomas Becket were not friends, at least not since Thomas' election to the see of Canterbury. He tells about Gilbert's calling Thomas a fool in public and of his slandering Thomas in Louis VII's audience as well as in front of the pope who reprimands him. Garnier even mentions that, in Northampton, Gilbert and

¹ Anne Duggan, *The Correspondence of Thomas Becket 1162-1170*, 1-2. 2000. Oxford, Clarendon, New York: Oxford UP. – Thomas Becket's assessment coincides with that of Alan of Tewkesbury, Mat 2: 352.

² See images at the end of this article. The name *Guarnerius* is given in a marginal note (*Nota illud esse guarnerii* "NB: that belongs to G.") of the manuscript Ludwig XIV.2 (1170–1180) of J. Paul Getty Museum (Los Angeles). This note is marked close to a canon describing a task to be performed by an *yconomus* ('procurator'). The writer Garnier, I think, is the same person as this *Guarnerius*. Far from being mainly interested in the saintly qualities of Thomas Becket, Garnier pays attention to the legal and financial matters in his life. He writes about Henry II's pilgrimage as if he were to inspect its financial profit (5921–6049) and, while in Canterbury, he takes time to dress an itemized list of Thomas Becket's belongings stolen right after his death (5660–5675). – Regarding marginal notes in Ludwig XIV.2, see Löfstedt 2015:194 sq.; regarding Garnier, Löfstedt 2019.

Guernes (<*warino* + *s*) is the calling name or nickname corresponding to any male full name of Frankish origin and starting with *warin-*.

Roger of York had given Henry II the advice that Thomas could be imprisoned once people had left the meeting (1826-1830); and that Thomas, while in exile, had nightmares about Gilbert (3861–3880).

Still, in Garnier's story, Gilbert was saved after he repented (Garnier 6011–6020).

As I have had the honor to publish the article "Thomas Becket's Letters from his Exile and their French Text" in *TCLA* (1 (2017): 12–108), I may be allowed to believe that the reader of this journal knows already that Garnier de Pont-Sainte-Maxence's *Vie de Saint Thomas*³ contains versified French drafts (not translations!) of some letters Thomas Becket sent from his exile. My comparison of these French drafts with the official Latin letters showed striking differences between them. The French drafts for two letters addressed to the king were clear, stern, but sincerely caring, the Latin verbose, unclear, and pompous, at times arrogant. This seemed to indicate that the Latin letters had been 'edited' by somebody hostile to the archbishop. The article suggested that one likely 'editor' would have been Gilbert Foliot who, as the king's confessor, might have had an exceptionally easy access to the letters addressed to the king.

Some secondary observations could also point to Gilbert's having an 'editorial' role in the transmission of Thomas Becket's correspondence.

Among the manuscripts of Thomas Becket's Latin correspondence, the Foliot-group (that "did not draw on Archetypes alpha and beta for their Becket-related correspondence, but on materials found in Foliot's own household", Duggan 2000,1:ci) shared more common features with Garnier's French letter texts than the other manuscripts. The similarities shared by the Foliot-group's Latin letters and Garnier's French letter drafts seem to support my theory of Gilbert Foliot's having had access to Thomas' letters in a form resembling Garnier's French text, and then 'editing' them.

An excellent writer himself, Gilbert had profited of Thomas' exile. He had become the *de facto* leader of the English Church. It was in his interest that Henry II had no warm feelings towards Thomas and did not ask him to return. 'Editing' Thomas' letters to the king making the letter-writer seem stupid and arrogant would have served that interest.

On the other hand, Garnier's French draft to the letter addressed to Gilbert seemed more severe than the official Latin version of the same letter and makes one wonder whether Gilbert's "name was cleared" for the Latin version.

³ The most important editions being E. Walberg 1922 (Lund: Gleerup) and 1936 (Paris: Honoré Champion. CFMA 77). For commentaries and translations consult also Jacques T. E. Thomas 2002. (Leuven: Peters) and I. Short 2013 (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies).

I think that Garnier never came to see the official Latin letters as he would have noticed the difference, and done some more research.⁴ He may also have been less forgiving towards Gilbert, if he had been presented the Foliot variants.

The only person to whom Garnier never forgave was Baal's other priest, *Eboracensis ille*, Roger de Pont-L'Évêque, archbishop of York, who hated Thomas Becket all since the two, as young men, worked in Canterbury at archbishop Theobald's chancellery. Garnier says that Roger of York had a criminal heart and the devil had taken his seat inside him:

...mult out felun quer et gros et surquidié
E li diables out dedenz lui pris sun sié (Garnier 4974–4975)

and Garnier gives a near-complete account of Roger's murderous scheme, a strategic masterpiece.

In order to understand it, however, we have to look at the bilingual medieval culture of transalpine Western Europe, where it was known, at least since the Council of Tours of the year 813, that Church Latin was not easily understood by non-school-educated people who had *lingua Romana rustica* (descending from the Latin spoken in the province) as their mother tongue.

Latin was the official international language, the language of all of the Roman Catholic Church and the schools, the language of truth and learning. The school-educated were *litterati*. The majority of laymen were not school-educated (*illitterati*); Latin was not their language; they used the vernacular of the region. As regular church-goers transalpine European laymen were quite used to listening to a mass they did not understand and interacting in the rituals according to the officiating clergy's instructions. They could only recite the Lord's Prayer and the Creed in their mother tongue. Now and then they were edified by a vernacular homily.

Latin stayed more or less the same, while vernaculars developed and changed. In England, two or three generations after the Norman invasion, the common vernacular of the ruling class was French (to some extent influenced by English).

⁴ My article "Une lettre de Thomas Becket" ([http:// www.ejournals.eu/ Romanica-Cracoviensia/2018/Tom-18-%30Numer-3/](http://www.ejournals.eu/Romanica-Cracoviensia/2018/Tom-18-%30Numer-3/)) adds some details regarding the French and Latin versions of the letter *Expectans*.

Latin was, still in the twelfth century, the (most important) written language and the language of official documents. Even lay people had their important documents (testaments, etc.) written in Latin. As shown above, I think that Thomas Becket drafted his letters in his – and the receiver's – mother tongue, although the official letters were preserved in a Latin version. Conversely, some administrative decree of immediate importance to the people, although preserved in Latin for posterity, must have been made known to the people by messengers using vernacular. The vernacular words are seldom recorded.⁵

The above has to be kept in mind when analysing larger text units. Speeches and conversations, e.g., recorded as parts of a longer narration in a given language may not have been originally "produced" in that language. For such passages one must try to find out the language actually used in the situation and the audience's mastery of that language, in short: who understood what was said.

Some hagiographers of Thomas Becket pay attention to the language used in situations they describe.

In front of the pope, one uses Latin. When Thomas Becket, fleeing from England, was granted audience by the pope, his first task there was to refute the Clarendon articles in a disputation against William of Pavia. The disputation demanding half a day was conducted in Latin and Thomas Becket spoke good Latin:

... li arcevesques comença a parler
E sa cause en latin gentement a mustrer (Garnier 2361–2362).
.....
Par bel latin adès a chascun point solu
Bien l'aveit en sa cause cil demi jur tenu (Garnier 2369–2370, also Edward Grim,
Mat 2:403).

A few days earlier, an English delegation had presented the English king's grievances to the pope and the nervous men's poor Latin is mentioned in many *Vitas*. Hilary of Chichester drew much attention when he finished his observations saying

"...non decuit, nec oportuit nec aliquando oportuebat."

⁵ There are exceptions, see "La Magna Carta, un document bilingue" in *Linguistique romane et linguistique indo-européenne: Mélanges offerts à Witold Manczak à l'occasion de son 90^e anniversaire*. Éd. par Leszek Bednarczuk, Anna Bochnakowa et al. 2014. Kraków-PAU/UJ. 329–337.

reports Alan of Tewkesbury, Mat 2: 338, and he underlines:

Ita grammatizabat Hilarius Cicestrensis dicendo 'oportuebat' .

Alan adds that everybody laughed at Hilarius who was told :

Male tandem uenisti ad portum (Mat 2: 339).⁶

Leaving out names of individuals, Garnier says sweepingly that some delegates spoke good Latin, but most of them did not, as they confused plural and singular, personal and impersonal constructions (Garnier 2256–2260).

In the English delegation there were not only members of high clergy – who were expected to have full command of Latin –, but also representatives of high nobility. One of them, the count (earl?) of Arundel spoke after the bishops and started by admitting that he did not understand Latin:

Quod locuti fuerint episcopi, nos illiterati penitus ignoramus 'We who are not school-educated do not have any idea of what the bishops might have said' (Alan of Tewkesbury, Mat 2:339),

and Alan tells us that the count thereafter spoke elegantly, but in his own language (ibid. 340) and that everybody liked his *modesta discretio*.

We notice that a member of the highest nobility of England, a person who is chosen to represent the country at a papal audience, does not understand spoken Latin, at the time the language of international diplomacy, and that the Latin presentations were not immediately translated for him; and we also see that members of the papal court could understand his French.

Pope Alexander III answers the count of Arundel: "*Scimus, fili comes...*" ('We know, my son count,...'), reply reported in Latin by Alan of Tewkesbury, as his entire *Vita* is in Latin. Here, we do not know whether the pope, who at that time was exiled in Sens (France), really spoke Latin to a man who did not understand Latin.

The pope's (<Orlando Bandinelli) childhood vernacular seems to have been Italian.⁷

⁶ The erroneous *oportuebat* reminds the crowd of *portus* 'port, harbor'.

⁷ There may have been clergymen mastering Latin perfectly, but unable to express themselves well in their childhood vernacular that they had not used after 'leaving the world' in their teens.

The count of Arundel was certainly not the only nobleman unable to understand Latin or express himself in Latin. In addition, those who had learned some Latin may have mastered the language only partially.

King Henry II of England had had a good education in his childhood (see Wikipedia), but as he got personally involved in defending his mother's right to the English crown during the Anarchy, and went to England to fight at the age of fourteen, one may wonder how easy it was for him later to use Latin *ex tempore* in various demanding situations. We find at least one public occasion where he preferred to use his mother tongue. Thomas Becket writes to Guillaume, archbishop of Sens:

...materna respondit lingua sic amfractus uerborum (quod familiare habet) inuertens ut simplicioribus uideretur omnia concedere, cautioribus autem immiscere conditiones ('he replied in his mother tongue, so twisting the meaning of words in his usual fashion that he seemed to the most simple-minded to be granting everything, while to the more cautious he seemed to include conditions' Duggan 2000,2: 1050, letter number 243).

The bilingualism had been taken into account in guest seating at Thomas Becket's formal dinners as well. It was customary that the archbishop's own dinner table listened to a Latin *lectio* when eating. As most lay guests did not understand Latin, they were served at their own table separately "so that they would not be irritated by the reading they did not understand".⁸

This kind of background lets us understand the admiration in John of Salisbury's words, when he describes Thomas Becket as perfectly bilingual, as somebody who could be learned and eloquent not only when talking with the literate (who spoke Latin), but also in a conversation with the illiterate (who used the vernacular). Thomas Becket used simple and clear words to express weighty thoughts, and so his audience liked to listen his preaching and it hit home:

...siue litteratis siue illitteratis colloqueretur, mirum in modum eruditus et eloquens apparebat et praedicatio eius tam pondere sententiarum quam puritate uerborum placens erat et efficax (Mat 2:308).

⁸ ...ne ipsos... non intelligentes molestaret lectio (Herbert of Bosham. Mat 3: 226).

This is also the background allowing Roger de Pont-L'Évêque, archbishop of York, to mastermind the murder in the cathedral. He would have known what language would have been used in a given meeting, or in a given document; and he would have understood who in the audience did or did not understand what was said or read.

Roger was also well aware of Henry II's weaknesses and he could use them for his own advantage. The king could absolutely not control his raging attacks that caused panic around him and distorted his own ability to think clearly, leaving him at the mercy of anybody not afraid of him. Proud and easily hurt, the king had also a ridiculously great need of being honored (*infra*).

There was one false narrative circulating, so it seems, already before Thomas' exile.

John of Salisbury, Thomas Becket's faithful friend, tells us that people close to the throne together with representatives of the highest clergy were interpreting Thomas' actions for the Church or certain features in his personal religious life as vices, saying that he was greedy when taking care of the Church, that he was vainglorious when living in austerity himself, etc., and John continues :

Nihil iam ab eo uel dici uel fieri poterat quod non malitia infelicitum hominum deprauaret, adeo quidem, ut regi persuaderent quod, si archiepiscopi potestas procederet, regia dignitas esset proculdubio peritura; et nisi sibi et heredibus suis prospiceret, is demum futurus esset rex, quem clerus eligeret, et quamdiu placeret archiepiscopo regnaturus

There was nothing he could say or do that the malice of those evil persons would not have destroyed. They went so far as to make the king believe that if the archbishop would be powerful, the regal dignity would fade away; and unless he himself would provide for his heirs, only a man chosen by the clergy could be king and the length of his reign would depend on the pleasure of the archbishop' (John of Salisbury, *Mat* 2: 310).

When it became evident that Roger, archbishop of York, was trying to expand his authority into the archdiocese of Canterbury, Roger received from the pope a letter that Edward Grim copied into his text (*Mat*. 2:406-407). There the pope forbids, by apostolic authority, all English clergymen to take part in the coronation of a new king without the permission of the archbishop of Canterbury and the convent of Canterbury who since times immemorial had the right to crown kings. This absolute prohibition did not hinder Roger to crown, in June 1170, the king's fifteen-year-old first-born son Henry, who had been called the Young King a long time already. Roger's transgression was aggravated by the fact that the Young King's coronation oath differed from the usual by not mentioning

any protection of the Church; however, the youth had to swear to keep Henry II's grandfather's laws.⁹ Subsequently, Roger was suspended and Gilbert Foliot and Jocelin of Salisbury who had participated in the coronation, were excommunicated by the pope.

Thomas Becket, returning to England, was charged to bring the pope's letter to those three. Arrived at the Channel, he heard that his life was in danger in England. Risking not to be able to enter the country himself, Thomas sent a footman of his to bring the papal letter to the bishops. Although it was a papal letter, nevertheless the bishops considered themselves punished by Thomas who then entered England a day or two later in early December.

Thomas was demanded to absolve the bishops immediately, but as he then wrote to the pope, he could not undo a higher judge's sentence; and nobody could invalidate a sentence of the Apostolic See:

Nos autem respondimus non esse iudicis inferioris, ut superioris sententiam soluat, et quod nulli omnino hominum licet infirmare, quod apostolica sedes decreuerit (Duggan 2000,1:1352–1353, letter 326; Thomas's letter is also included in his *Vita* by Edward Grim, Mat 2: 425; similar text in Garnier 4902-4905 letter 326).

Such an answer was not accepted, although Thomas also promised his personal help and support to the bishops of London and Salisbury. Rather, Thomas' excommunication (as it was called) of the bishops who had officiated at the coronation was said by his enemies to signify that he denied the Young King's right to his crown¹⁰, and they added maliciously that Thomas had returned from the exile in order to destroy the king's plans and establishments:

inimici iustitiae uirum Dei calumniati sunt... de exilio repedasse ut regis propositum et instituta dissolueret (Edward Grim Mat, 2: 426).

⁹ ...nulla ex more de conseruanda ecclesiae libertate mentio facta est (Edward Grim, Mat 2:407; see also William of Canterbury Mat 1:93)

¹⁰ An impossible accusation. Thomas, whose last tasks as Lord Chancellor included securing from the nobility their fealty oaths and homages for little prince Henry (Edward Grim Mat 2:366), liked the boy whose education he had supervised (FitzStephen Mat. 3:22). Thomas was hurt and sad for not having been able to crown the young prince.

Thomas wanted to see the Young King who at the moment was in Winchester, at a meeting called together by Roger, Gilbert and Jocelin, and by Geoffrey Ridel, archdeacon of Canterbury, but an eager helper and spokesman to Roger, archbishop of York. Thomas sent a messenger before him with a letter announcing his arrival and asking for an audience. The audience was denied. William of Canterbury relates the objection to this decision by Reinald, earl of Cornwall.¹¹ The old statesman pays attention to Thomas' manner of moving around in England. Is he surrounded by several units of armed foreigners? No, he arrives with only a few people of his own household and his behavior is that of a clergyman. Referring to Thomas' letter, Reinald adds that the Young King is the person dearest to Thomas and concludes that he does not understand why a person who is allowed to return from exile, would not be allowed to be heard:

Aduertamus igitur quando, cur, quo duce, repatriauerit is de quo conferimus...Si copias armatorum aligenarum induxisset, posset in indigenis non immerito suspectus haberi. Nunc uero paucis admodum familiaribus contentus, religiosae conuersationis, pastoralis baculo subnixus, pacem ferens, pacemque promittens, suam optat praesentiam dominumque suum uidere,... cui, sicut praestito iuramento testatur, in dilectione neminem mortalium aequiparat. Igitur non uideo qualiter illi de ratione prohibeatur accessus. Non aduerto quare non permittatur audiri qui permissus est ab exilio reuocari (William of Canterbury, Mat 1: 112).

Reinald's message was certainly understood by Roger of York and his messenger Geoffrey Ridel. Nevertheless, referring to an (imaginary) conversation with Henry II, "who did not wish his son to talk with somebody who wanted to take away his crown" Geoffrey made the teenage king deny audience to his old friend. With Geoffrey's 'help' he also sent messengers to Thomas Becket, making him return to Canterbury. Thomas Becket was told by them:

*sic mandatur tibi a domino rege: Pacem ille iniit tecum, et tu primus rupisti foedera pacis et pactum praeuaricatus es, qui domesticos regis et pontifices ab ecclesia segregasti et militum manu per urbes regias armatus ingredis (Edward Grim, Mat 2: 427; similar text in Garnier 4881–4925).*¹²

¹¹ Illegitimate son to Henry I, hence the Empress'half-brother and a 'half-uncle' to Henry II.

¹² The Young King, still a young boy, was used to cover power-hungry men's crimes says Garnier (6073–6075).

The main accusations against Thomas are now prepared: Thomas' denying the Young King's right to his crown (impossible, as Thomas told them himself), his excommunication of the bishops (done by the pope) and people of the king's household, and his marching with a military unit (imaginary accusation inspired maybe by Reinald of Cornwall's statement of the opposite).¹³

Following Roger of York's plan, the three bishops punished by the pope went to King Henry II who was in Normandy. Garnier tells us that, as soon as they landed, they sent the pope's Latin letter – where they themselves were punished – to the king. Did Roger also include a commentary of his own which accused Thomas? What we know is that the king had very much wanted his son to be crowned even against a papal defense, and that he might have been afraid of some papal punishment himself. The letter arrived at Bur-le Roi on the day before Christmas 1170, when the king already was celebrating with his men (and no doubt with some strong Christmas ale). Upon reading it, the king exploded in fury and complained about Thomas: "he has offended my family and my entire kingdom!". And Henry II's faithful men echoed the king's laments, cursing Thomas and promising to revenge the king's shame. (A lively description of the situation in Garnier 5011–5040).

When the bishops then arrived, they threw themselves at the king's feet and wailed in front of him. The king's face took a new expression and he asked them to stand up. The scene was ready for Roger to present accusations against Thomas. (The other two, being excommunicated, were forbidden to talk.) Edward Grim lets Roger of York say directly to the king that Thomas who now has acted *ad regis et regni dedecus* ('bringing shame to king and country', Mat 2:428-429) might try something worse, if the king takes this impudence patiently in his stride.¹⁴ Garnier lets Roger assure the king that Thomas had excommunicated everybody who took part in the Young King's coronation. That causes Henry II to react "In that case, my position is weak, God's eyes, I want him to be crowned, I consent to it!" And Roger seems to present, falsely, the king's excommunication as a *fait accompli* "Sir, when you have to go with us into this misery, then the pain is easier for us

¹³ In Thomas's retinue, there were five shields, five battle-horses and five spears (FitzStephen Mat 3: 124).

¹⁴ *Adiiciunt accusantes* (Roger's group) *quod maius aliquid audebit adhuc, si istam rex patienter portauerit praesumptionem* (Edward Grim, Mat. 2: 429).

to bear".¹⁵ Roger continues: "He throws out from the Church your brave men, excommunicates your bishops, and that is not all. Since he came to England, he crosses your lands with a big band of armed knights and squires" (Garnier 5063–5070). After Roger's speech, the pope's Latin letter was read for everybody to hear. Edward Grim ends the scene describing the incontrollable rage tormenting Henry II who had to retreat to his private room, repeating like a madman (*amens*) a reproach addressed to his men who had allowed him to be made a fool of by a plebeian cleric:

Talibus circumuentus rex, et uelut amens factus, nec se capiens pro furore,
nescius quid obiicere, haec iteratis uicibus dixisse fertur "Inertes ac miseros
homines enutriui et exi in regno meo qui nec fidem ferunt domino suo, quem a
plebeo quodam clerico tam probrose patiuntur illudi". Dixit et e medio
secedens... locum familiarem petiit...(Edward Grim 2: 429).

The king, so it seems, did not question any detail in the report. His men were not trained in Latin; and when the pope's letter was read aloud, they did not even understand that the excommunicating person was the pope rather than Thomas Becket. They had seen and heard the king's horrible breakdown; they had listened to the grave accusations presented by the archbishop of York and everybody in the room shouted that they wished to revenge the king's shame on Thomas Becket.

Four men actually left for Canterbury. Archbishop Roger of York went out with them and emboldened them¹⁶: the entire kingdom was in bad shape and suffered because of Thomas; if only he were dead, everything would calm down. Roger would himself be responsible of any sin that the men's task could possibly force them to commit.¹⁷ He told

¹⁵ *Sire, fait l'arcevesques, quant vus estuet (present!) partir/ A la grevance od nus, mielz le poum souffrir* (Garnier 5061-5062).

¹⁶ Edward Grim, whose work is dated to 1172, relates these events roughly in the same way as Garnier whose work was finished only a couple of years later (1174) when Thomas already was canonized (1173). Edward, however, does not call Roger by name. The person who emboldens the four knights to revenge the king's shame is *qui homicida fuit ab initio* ('the one who was the murderer from the very beginning') and this unnamed one *qui facinus inspirauit* ('who incited them to the crime'), *Facilitatem quoque tribuit ad perpetrandum* ('also helped them to perpetuate it') (Mat 2: 429). Garnier, a Frenchman, could write freely about English things; Edward was an Englishman, and Roger, after a short punishment, was again the archbishop of York. He died only in 1181.

¹⁷ *Par Thomas est li regnes trublez e empeiriez / S'il esteit mort, ço dit, tut sereit apaisiez / De quanqu'il en ferunt / Prent sur sei les pechiez* (Garnier 5128–5130).

them exactly what they would have to say to Thomas and he gave to each of them sixty marks (Garnier 5121–5133).

Roger seems to have told them what to say not only orally, but also in writing. Edward Grim, who was visiting Thomas Becket in Canterbury, was included in the meeting where one of the four recited "the King's message" to the archbishop. Here is Edward's report of its contents:

Rex, inter vos pace reformata liberum te, querelis omnibus consopitis, ad propriam sedem, ut poposcisti, remisit; et tu e contrario prioribus iniuriis contemptum adiiciens, violato pacis foedere, superbe aduersus dominum tuum tibi ipsi in malum operatus es. Nam quorum ministerio regis filius coronatus est, et regni sublimatus honore, pertinacis animi tumore ductus suspensionis sententia condemnasti, ministros quoque regis quorum consiliis et prudentia tractantur negotia regni, vinculo anathematis innodasti; ut ex his manifestum sit quoniam filii regis coronam auferres, si facultas adesset. Iam enim molitiones tuae et instantia, ut ad effectum perduceres quod contra dominum tuum excogitasti, omnibus innotuere. Super his igitur in praesentia regis responsurus si uenire dignaris, edicito. Ad hoc enim missi sumus. (Edward Grim, Mat 2: 431)

Pronounced either in Latin (as reported in Edward Grim's Latin *Vita* where the verb used is *recitare*) considering the clerical audience, or in the French vernacular of the men themselves, this message is not written by the king (referred to in the third person) nor put together by the men whom the king is said to have sent: they would not have mastered the complicated syntax of this pompous piece of questionable eloquence. It begins by stating that the King had graciously allowed Thomas to return as he had demanded. But Thomas had acted contemptuously against his overlord and broken the peace agreement. Thereafter, Thomas is again accused of suspension of bishops (done by the pope) and of wishing to take away the Young King's crown. The big band of armed men is left out: it would not have fitted the situation, where the archbishop, surrounded by Canterbury clerics and monks, was peacefully listening to a presentation. The speech ends by Thomas' being invited to answer for his actions in the king's presence, which Thomas declines as he had been forbidden to enter royal domains.¹⁸

¹⁸The four knights do not know that Geoffrey Ridel – acting by order of Roger of York – had forbidden Thomas to enter any royal towns. They did not know that they in fact had been sent to attack Thomas in Canterbury. They did not know that their task would cause them to be excommunicated (Second

It was of course in vain that Thomas refuted the accusations. The men followed 'the king's orders' and, after 'revenging the king's shame' (by killing the archbishop, nearly severing Edward Grim's arm, and desecrating the cathedral during Christmas), they proudly shouted the royal battle cry *Reaus* (< *regales* 'King's men' Garnier 5643; Edward Grim Mat 2:439) .– They were soon to be excommunicated.

Edward Grim tells us that Henry II had tried to stop the four and sent people after them, as soon as he noticed that they had left the Christmas gathering (which may have happened while he himself was in his private room trying to calm down). When he then was informed about Thomas' murder, he seemed to "become totally confused, sorrow dimmed his mind, and, chasing away every thought, the horror of the committed crime filled their place"¹⁹ (Edward Grim Mat 2:429). William of Canterbury writes that the king sent two of his clerics to Canterbury to tell the monks that he did try to stop the men from fulfilling their plan (Mat 1: 124–126). These reports can also be compared to the account given by the bishop of Bayeux and found in Herbert of Bosham's (Mat 3: 541-542) and Thomas de Froidmont's (Schmidt 1991:176) hagiographies: the king lost his will to live.

Garnier ends his story by describing in detail the King's pilgrimage (1174) to Canterbury where he was whipped by the bishop of London (Gilbert Foliot) and Canterbury clergy and monks. God did not punish England, Garnier says, because King Henry II presented himself as the cause of everything, attoned everything himself, and gave the Church its (judicial) liberty (5726–5730).

In comparison with the above, Henry II's letter to the pope (1171) is perplexing. After the formal greetings one reads:

Ob reuerentiam Romanae ecclesiae et amorem uestrum, quem Deo teste
fideliter quaesiui et constanter usque modo seruauui, Thomae Cantuariensi

Lateran Council , 1139, § 15: "Anyone laying violent hands on a cleric or monk shall be anathematized". We can safely assume that the archbishop of York knew all of this. He may also have known that the four were eager to show their loyalty to Henry II as their reputation might have been tarnished by their earlier associations to King Stephen or Scotland (cf. Nicholas Vincent 2003: 214–215).

¹⁹ ... *tanta eius animum praeoccupauit confusio, turbauit maestitia, absorbuuit pariter et possedit horror facinoris inauditi...*(Edward Grim, Mat 2: 429)

archiepiscopo, iuxta vestri formam mandati, pacem et possessionum suarum plenam restitutionem indulsi²⁰, et cum honesto commeatu in Angliam transfretare concessi. Ipse uero in ingressu suo non pacis laetitiam, sed ignem portauit et gladium, dum contra me de regno et corona proposuit quaestionem. Insuper meos seruietes passim sine causa excommunicare aggressus est. Tantam igitur proteruitatem homines non ferentes excommunicati et alii de Anglia irruerunt in eum et, (quod dicere sine dolore non ualeo) occiderunt. Quia igitur iram quam contra illum dudum conceperam timeo causam huic maleficio praestitisse, Deo teste grauiter sum turbatus. Et quia in hoc facto plus famae meae quam conscientiae timeo, rogo serenitatem uestram ut in hoc articulo me salubris consilii medicamine foueatis. (Mat 7: 440).

This letter was not written personally by the king. Henry II would not have come up with the request of a 'soothing treatment with the medicine of (the Pope's) healing counsel.'

Interestingly, the letter reminds us of something we had already seen.

The combination of fire and sword refers to armed aggression. Roger of York had told the king of that same danger ('Since he came to England, he crosses your lands with a big band of armed knights and squires'). The knights—sent by the Young King to forbid Thomas access to royal domains—do likewise ('You crisscross he country with an armed unit'): the Young King had heard this from Geoffrey Ridel; and Geoffrey's master was Roger.

In those two contexts, as in this letter, Thomas is accused of questioning the royal family's right to their crown; this point was also taken up in the message to Thomas recited by the killer knights who had received their instructions from Roger.

Thomas' misuse of ecclesiastical punishments was mentioned by Roger to Henry II, by the Young King's messengers to Thomas, and the killer knights' message to Thomas. While this accusation comes up in this royal letter to the pope as well, its presentation is different in one detail; Thomas is not accused of punishing bishops, but royal officials (*meos seruietes*). The letter-writer (or, rather, his helper?) seems to know that the bishops had been punished by the pope himself.

²⁰ One of Henry II's empty promises, whose lack of fulfillment he did not pay any attention to. Simultaneously with this letter, the pope got a letter from Guillaume, archbishop of Sens, who writes: *Scimus enim quod possessiones sicut promiserat restituit, nec securitatem, sicut mors martyris indicat, praestitit* (Mat 7:441).

In this letter Henry deeply regrets the mere possibility of having caused the murder by his anger. He does so without discussing the immediate situation where he was so desastrously infuriated. The three prelates' visit is not mentioned.

The end of this letter can be attributed to a very intelligent and cold-blooded liar. Among the four killers, there was no one recently excommunicated and no one who had joined the group in England – the excommunicated Brocs who did live in England, were not Thomas' murderers (only the murderers' helpers). All four knights who killed the archbishop came from the king's Norman court where the murder had been planned. – Edward Grim's and William of Canterbury's stories state that the king wanted to catch and bring back the four men as soon as he noticed that they had left, but this letter would rather indicate that he did not know who they were and from where they came. This was certainly the letter-writer's (helper's) intention. After sending this letter to the pope, the king could not openly help them, or even say he knew those poor men who committed an atrocious crime in order to revenge the king's shame. The men were alone.

And Roger, the archbishop of York, who had declared himself ready to take the responsibility for any sin the knights may be forced to commit? Would it not have been more prudent for him to stay a while longer in close contact with the king? Among other things he could have (directly or indirectly) helped the king to write this self-incriminating letter to the pope... The letter seems to complete Roger's own plan as it sweeps away his vestiges. After the king had sent off this letter, the men could not refer to Roger as somebody who had emboldened them to act as the king's chosen men. Really? How so? The king does not even know these men...

As mentioned in the beginning, Thomas Becket did not think that his difficulties were in first place due to Henry II, when he wrote to the pope:

Quod tamen non tam illi (sc. to the English king) credimus imputandum quam sacerdotibus Baal... qui tocius discordie incentores ab initio extiterunt. Sed horum omnium primicerii sunt Eboracensis ille et episcopus Lundonensis...

In *TCLA*, Vol. 1, Nr. 1, February 2017 (16-125) and in this article I have shown that it is possible to corroborate the intuition or knowledge Thomas shares with the Pope with the information found in his earliest hagiographies.

For me, it is more difficult to explain Thomas's murder in first hand as the result of a personal antipathy between the king and the archbishop.

Thomas Becket had recently become archdeacon of Canterbury (1154) when King Stephen died and Henry Fitz Empress (son to Geoffrey d'Anjou and Empress Matilda, Stephen's cousin) became Henry II at the age of 21. Archbishop Theobald did not trust the very young king, who might have been willing to oppress the Church and who also seemed to be surrounded by evil counselors and arrogant courtiers. So the archbishop decided that his own trusted archdeacon would become the king's chancellor:

... elaboratum est ab antedicto archiepiscopo ut archidiaconus suus regni cancellarius efficeretur...: cancellarium procurabat in curia ordinari cuius ope et opera noui regis, ne saeuiret in ecclesiam, impetum cohiberet et consilii sui temperaret malitiam et reprimeret audaciam officialium ("...by whose (Thomas') help he (Theobald) would control the you king's frenzy...John of Salisbury, Mat 2:304).

Regarding Thomas' new position, Theobald was helped by Bishop Henry of Winchester (Henri de Blois, King Stephen's brother, Fitzstephen, Mat 3:17).²¹

Thomas, 13 years Henry II's senior, turned out to be an excellent chancellor and, when needed, a competent military leader and a reliable counselor to the king, whose trusted friend he became. There was only one thing, I think, that Henry decided to do against the counsel of Thomas. It was to oblige the convent of Canterbury to elect Thomas to become their archbishop. Henry II ignored the fact that the archbishop of Canterbury could not be his chancellor. When Thomas returned his chancellor's seal and began working in first hand for the Church, he lost the king's trust, his absolute, childish trust. Thomas's place was filled by other, less trustworthy persons.

Theobald was proven right not to consider the king to be reliable without a reliable chancellor. At the end of his life, Thomas himself wished that the king get honest counselors and become reliable himself (Garnier 4262–4264).

Thomas, appointed by Theobald to guide the young Henry II to be aware of the Church's rights, had no doubt been obedient during his time as a chancellor: the Church had not suffered in a way Theobald had feared and the kingdom had thrived in war and peace.

²¹ See also Edward Grim Mat 2:363–364; Garnier 281–282;. Could some of the royal officials' hostility towards Archbishop Thomas Becket be taken as their revenge on the restraint exercised by Chancellor Thomas Becket?

Thomas respected the king²², and planned and worked for the king, while protecting the Church.

Unfortunately, the king had not been obliged to learn to listen to suggestions and analyse and discuss them in order to make well prepared decisions and justified and feasible plans.

Thomas Becket's hagiographies, certainly biased in favor of Thomas, present Henry II (who laid the foundation to English Common Law!) as somebody who needed an educator. They paint an alarming picture of the king's rather irresponsible governing.

Henry II acts first and thinks afterwards, if at all. He makes Thomas archbishop of Canterbury and realizes only afterwards that he has lost a good chancellor, as a civil servant cannot be archbishop.

Henry II had to make sure that the crown of England would stay in his family and so he had his young son crowned against a papal prohibition. After this, he was afraid of being excommunicated. – His young son represents him in England, but the communication between father and son is not secured and Geoffrey Ridel can lie to the Young King (*supra*).

He had made peace with Thomas before Thomas' return, but when Thomas returned, he could easily be made to believe (again?) that Thomas would take away his son's crown and that Thomas marched around in England with a sizeable unit of armed men. As he did not question anything in Roger of York's story presenting these accusations (*supra*), one concludes that he did not remember or trust his own judgement.

Henry II is presented as careless and stubborn. After losing his chancellor Thomas, Henry II seems to be unaware of the Church's judicial autonomy and he neglected it²³. The very first clashes between the king and his archbishop occurred when the king wanted to make the Church pay taxes to the crown (question of *aie al vescunte*, Garnier

²² As I attribute to Thomas Becket the *Decretum* translation apparently destined for a lay ruler, I cannot but think that Thomas Becket respected the obvious recipient (Henry II), his intelligence, his willingness to learn and find a way to collaborate with the Church for the good of his country; and that Thomas understood the challenge the king was facing and that he thought the king's success was worth his own Herculean task.

²³ As Henry's reaching for his mother tongue in a difficult situation would point to a less-than-perfect mastery of Latin, this total ignorance of canon law would explain his needing a French translation of Gratian's *Decretum*.

751–770) and have a clergyman, acquitted in an ecclesiastical court, stand trial before a lay judge (question of *Philippe de Broï*, Garnier 771-815).

While trying to make everybody accept his grandfather's laws, did Henry II know them himself? Thomas who seems to have been using old English laws when punishing Philippe de Broï²⁴, could not accept Clarendon articles, that the king presented as his grandfather's laws (Garnier 1736–1738, e.g.). Thomas's objection is corroborated by modern research.²⁵

Henry II's misuse of his own judiciary power may be in part due to his ignorance. What paragraph would support the king's decision to deny, to a sick man, his *essoïn* ('excuse for nonappearance in court')(Edward Grim Mat 2: 391), or, to an archbishop, his absence from a lay court on the day of Holy Cross (Fitzstephen Mat 3: 50), absence formally demanded (*absentia, non contumacia* Fitzstephen Mat 3:64), only to accuse him of contempt of court and condemn him to heavy fines? for the payment of which some bishops presented themselves as pledges.²⁶

Refusing the excuse is against secular laws, having clergymen stand before a lay judge is against canon law.

Henry II is also presented as despotic and completely lacking in self-control²⁷:

When infuriated, he wants to bring all clergy to trial (Garnier 1701–1705).

He wants to use his judiciary power against Thomas demanding that he give accounts for all the money used during his time as a chancellor, although Thomas was by a royal order acquitted of this secular accountability before he could be consecrated archbishop. Then,

²⁴ Compare Garnier 806–815, also Edward Grim Mat 2: 375, with *Leis Willelme* § 10.2, and *Leges Henrici Primi* § 36, both in Liebermann I. – In detail in Löfstedt 2019:391 sq.

²⁵ The Constitutions were claimed to restore the judicial customs observed during the reign of Henry I (1100–1135), while in fact they were a part of Henry II's larger expansion of royal jurisdiction into the Church and civil law, which was a defining aspect of his reign (Wikisource: Constitutions of Clarendon).

²⁶ The pledge money seems to have amounted to 500 marks. Thomas fled the country very soon after this wrong condemnation. He expected the king to dismiss the case and nullify the sentence and return the 500 marks at the time of the reconciliation (Garnier 4454-4455; 4476-4480; 4529–4530). Thomas's and his men's safe stay in England seemed to depend on those 500 marks (Garnier 4276–4280).

²⁷ In his poem presented to Henry II, FitzStephen makes the king pray to God saying: *Cum in ira mente dira interdum efferueo/ Deus care, moderare in me quod non ualeo* ('When, in anger, my wild mind boils over, dear God, moderate what I cannot moderate', Mat. 3:80).

the king wanted to sue Thomas for breaking his fealty oath, although Thomas was not his vassal ... (Garnier 1883–1890).

Henry II's decision to force all persons close to Thomas Becket to leave England – actually carried out by Randolph del Broc – or his menace to expel all Cistercians from the country, since Thomas Becket lived as a guest at the Cistercian abbey of Pontigny, illustrate the same thoughtless, cruel despotism.

Henry II's erratic behavior causes him to be corrected, often by Thomas who was given this 'educator role' by Theobald, and who even as an archbishop never ceased being the king's friendly and firm advisor. When the king says that his grandfather used to condemn criminal clerics to death, Thomas corrects him by saying that he knew of only one execution of a clergyman by Henry I and that it certainly was not a recommendable example of justice.²⁸

Thomas was not the only one to criticize Henry II. When Henry II wants to make Thomas give him a new account of his expenditures as a chancellor, he is corrected and even warned by Bishop Henry of Winchester (Garnier 1461–1505). At the end of the Northampton meeting, he is told by the count of Leicester to give attention to the crowd's behavior towards the archbishop or else he might get reprimanded or come to shame himself.

The king's normal reaction to anything going against his wishes, and certainly to a rebuke, is that "nobody has ever been treated as badly as I have been" and "why are people causing me such shame", followed maybe by some rage attack. It took courage to be a good counselor to a person so unable to listen to criticizing advice. Hence, I think, people around him preferred to only 'honor' him, encouraging him to do whatever he wanted to do, or just slightly redirecting his chosen path:

Pur les oilz Deu, fait il, ne volt acunte rendre ?

E si est mis huem liges: jugement en voil prendre/

– Sire, funt it, mais d'el...

("...For God's eyes, he said, he does not want to give account? he is my vassal. I want to sentence him!" – Yes, sir, but for something else" Garnier 1853–1855)

²⁸ *Quod asseritur auum uestrum...in clericorum necem saeuisse, subita quadam praesumptione et semel id factum cognouimus; sed incongruum ualde est ab his sumi exempla iustitiae qui quicquid propria elegerant libertate pro legibus affirmabant* (EG Mat 2: 387–388). – If Henry did not feel that Thomas remained his sincere friend, these corrections might have irritated him.

Albeit less pointedly, as if in passing, the hagiographies also give evidence of Henry's being overly high-strung and sometimes wishing to avoid people.

Roger's story at Bur-le-Roi had caused Henry II to suffer such an attack of rage that he had to leave his Christmas gathering to seek calm in his private room. A somewhat similar situation could be witnessed at the Northampton meeting when Thomas' resistance to the Clarendon articles was discussed: the King never even entered the meeting room (Garnier 1661–1695). Apparently, the King did not want to be seen in a situation that he could not master.

The same texts teach us that Henry did not like England.

In the second meeting of Montmirail the king wanted the archbishop to honor him in the way his predecessors had been honored by earlier archbishops (Alan of Tewkesbury Mat 2: 348), adding that it was necessary that his subjects be afraid of him, and that was why he had to be severe and steadfast; he reigned over untrustworthy people and that is why he had to show a stern face (Garnier 4971–4115).

Before the Young King's coronation Henry II was king of England, but personally he preferred to live on the continent. England was ruled according to his orders –more or less– by his officials whose actions he did not (care to) control. He depended on his officials' and counselors' information.²⁹ Henry II did not personally come to England to prepare Thomas Becket's consecration or, later, to find out details leading to the murder in the cathedral. We also learn that it had been agreed that several bishops elected in England should then be consecrated on the continent (Garnier 4756-4790; Edward Grim Mat 2:426).

I think that Henry II's early experiences of England had caused him to avoid the country. He grew up during the civil war between two pretenders to the throne: his mother the Empress Matilda (daughter of Henry I) and King Stephen (nephew to Henry I). It was a lawless time called the Anarchy (1138–1153), involving battles and sieges, ambushes and treasons. Henry "Fitz Empress" knew about his mother's difficulties and got involved in

²⁹To assure a royal presence in England, he had his first-born son Henry called the Young King and seated onto England's throne to preside over the justices governing the country. Henry the Young King was seven years old when Bishop Henry of Winchester presented the archbishop-elect Thomas Becket to the government demanding that Thomas be freed of all accountability related to his earlier position as Lord Chancellor. (Edward Grim Mat 2: 367; Garnier 525-529; Fitzstephen Mat 3:35).

the war when he was only fourteen years old.³⁰ His first expedition was not a military success, but it may have taught him not to trust anybody, and it may have shown him how easily people in England were switching sides and changing fealties.

It would be easy to see Henry Fitz Empress as a tragic personality. He was predestined to continue Henry I's dynasty, as Henry I did not have surviving legitimate sons. Henry Fitz Empress was born into a marriage arranged by Henry I, for his daughter Matilda to have a son. He was welcomed by Henry I, but the grandfather died when the boy was three. He was adored by his mother Matilda, but she was overwhelmed by her efforts to hold on to the crown of England. Henry Fitz Empress' was certainly not a safe, happy and trusting childhood. The boy went repeatedly to England in his teens to fight for his mother's rights. When he then became heir to the English throne at the age of twenty (after inheriting the continental domains of his father, Geoffrey d'Anjou, and marrying the duchess of Aquitania), he was surrounded by people ready to counsel him, but in reality desiring to profit by his position and his wealth.

After Henry II's coronation, archbishop Theobald arranged a good chancellor, Thomas Becket, to serve him. Most likely, Thomas' chancellor years were the happiest in Henry's life. Was not Thomas the big brother who took care of everything and made England a safe place? Consequently, Thomas' leaving the immediate royal service caused a deep disappointment for Henry, an ill-boding return into an existence where he could not trust anybody.

The void after Thomas was filled by other people, who then wanted to cling to their position by trying to kill all friendship between the king and his archbishop.³¹

Henry II only wanted Thomas to honor him, but when the commoner-archbishop was killed in his Cathedral, the king is told to have lost his will to live.

History is written by the winners. And the winners were the two envious and ambitious sons of Baal who profited of two myths that they helped to create: that Thomas, the King's

³⁰This brave (or fool-hardy?) youth had enlisted some mercenaries for his first military expedition into England (Wikipedia quoting Barlow p. 180.) A second, more successful, expedition followed two years later.

³¹See also Edward Grim Mat 2:363–364; Garnier 281–282;. Could some of the royal officials' hostility towards Archbishop Thomas Becket be taken as their revenge on the restraint exercised by Chancellor Thomas Becket?

former friend, now was his and the royal family's dangerous enemy and that the King had wanted and even ordered Thomas Becket to be killed.

Once Henry II was considered guilty of Thomas's murder, Roger of York could clear his name by an oath with three co-jurors (*quarta manu iuratorum*, Mat 7: 502). The King's confessor, Gilbert Foliot, could then, together with Canterbury monks, punish the King by a ceremonial whipping.

Fig. 1

diu actiones
ea cadat. nec
q. soluturus
di omnino det
m. Co. h. a. ty
Si yconomia
a cuiq. certan
rum. s. sine v
tum. tempo
peticione pst
q; que^{re}nt. su
desiderant pot
inat ycono
pus man q.
nifestum sit
sue opleto s
mortis su^{er}u

Non illud est quatuor.
3

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

The first two pictures courtesy of Dr. Elizabeth Morrison, Senior Curator of Manuscripts, J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles, the last, my own photo of the text as seen on a copy printed from a microfilm of the manuscript Ludwig XIV.2.

The marginal note states *Nota illud esse guarnerii* 'NB That belongs to Garnier' The adjacent text Decr. C 10 q 2 c 2 § 11 reads *Si yconomus ecclesiae prospexerit expedire, ut cuiquam desideranti certarum possessionum atque prediorum... ad ius ecclesiasticum pertinentium temporalis ususfructus possessio prestatetur...pacta cum eo, qui hoc elegerit, ineat yconomus*

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